

Electrode Photopotential. Part I

K. M. Joshi and A. B. Karnik

The rise and decay curves for photopotentials in the metal/acetophenone system in various solvents have been investigated. The photopotentials have been found to depend on the nature of solvent and electrode material. Pure acetophenone or acetophenone in non-polar solvents does not exhibit any photopotentials. Free-radical formation is concluded to be one of the causes of the photopotential.

Photopotentials are observed when one of the electrodes in an electrochemical system is irradiated by light of suitable frequency. Copeland *et al.*¹ have pointed out that the phenomenon is of a general nature observed in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions and with several different types of electrodes including oxide-coated metal electrodes. Levin and White² have made an extensive study of this effect in organic solvents and their results show that photopotentials are sensitive to dissolved oxygen. Harty³ worked with the Grignard reagents in organic solvents; Hilson and Rideal⁴ observed large photopotentials with dye solutions. The effect of intensive drying on the photopotentials was studied by Audubert⁵ who observed that photopotentials were reduced to almost zero in some cases; hence the effect was attributed to the photolysis of water. Surash and Hercules⁶ worked with anthraquinone in ethanol and pointed out that the electro-active species was a free radical formed by photochemical reaction in solution, the electrode acting as an inert electrode as in a redox system. A theory based on thermionic work function of the metal has been outlined by Bockris⁷ for equilibrium photopotentials. The present investigation deals with acetophenone/organic solvents system and the effect of electrode material, polar and non-polar solvents, viscosity, etc. has been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

The cell used in the work is shown in Fig. 1. It was made of Pyrex glass and provided with standard joints. The limb 'A' contains Ag/AgCl electrode, as also inlet and outlet for nitrogen. The nitrogen inlet tube was drawn to a jet and turned right angles towards the platinum electrode to facilitate efficient stirring. The limb containing the reference

1. *Chem. Rev.*, 1942, **31**, 177.
2. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 417.
3. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, **39**, 355.
4. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1940, **199A**, 295.
5. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1927, **24**, 357.
6. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 1602.
7. "Modern Aspects of Electrochemistry", Butterworth, 1954, p. 243.

electrode was covered with black insulating tape to avoid exposure of light to the reference electrode. The short limb 'B' was provided with a quartz window. The platinum electrode was 3 mm long and 0.5 mm in dia. platinum wire fused in a glass tube and was positioned near the quartz window.

FIG. 1

1. Silver/silver chloride electrode.
2. Tube for maintaining nitrogen atmosphere above the solution.
3. Tube for bubbling nitrogen.
7. Quartz window.
8. Platinum electrode.

Ag/AgCl electrode was prepared according to standard specifications⁸. The electrode was checked against standard calomel electrode from time to time.

The source of illumination was a G.E.C. 100-watt mercury vapour lamp type, H-4, of which the outer glass cover was removed. The light from the source was collimated by means of circular slits and focussed on the platinum electrode by a short-focus quartz lens. The distance between the source and the lens was 9.5 cm and the distance between the lens and electrode was 7.7 cm. The incident light was examined by a Hilger quartz spectrograph and was found to contain strong 3131, 3650, 4046, 4078 Å lines.

Nitrogen for deoxygenation of the electrolyte was the cylinder gas purified in the conventional manner as in polarographic work. The gas was bubbled through the solvent before being led to the cell.

Acetophenone used was of Narden Holland pure grade and was purified twice by distillation. The solvents used were of A. R. quality, further purified by redistillation.

Potentials were measured on a Radiometer pH-meter using half millivolt scale. The instrument was checked from time to time against standard potentials obtained from calibrated potentiometer.

The electrodes used were platinum, gold-plated platinum, silver, nickel, and copper. Platinum was cleaned with hot chromic acid and washed. It was cathodised for 15 min., washed, dried, and used. Nickel, gold, and copper were deposited electrolytically on platinum from usual plating solutions. Silver wire, sealed in glass with Araldite, was used as silver electrode after cleaning with hot nitric acid, washing, and drying.

Procedure.—The cell was filled with the solution and purified nitrogen was bubbled for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reference and platinum electrodes were connected to the pH-meter. The shutter on the light source housing was opened, making radiation incident on the electrode. The photopotentials were read at every ten seconds. When the photopotential was steady for some time, the shutter was closed and decay of potential with time recorded. The maximum photopotentials recorded are reproducible within ± 5 mv.

8. David *et al.*, "Reference Electrodes: Theory and Practice", Academic Press, New York and London, 1961.

TABLE I

Acetophenone (0.012 <i>M</i>) in solvent.	Photopotentials (max.).	Acetophenone (0.012 <i>M</i>) in solvent.	Photopotentials (max.).
Ethanol	-210 mv	Benzene	Nil
<i>n</i> -Propanol	-210	10% Cyclohexane + 90% ethanol	-198 mv
Isopropanol	-120	25 " + 75 "	-115
<i>n</i> -Butanol	-185	50 " + 50 "	-65
90% Ethanol + 10% benzene	-185	Cyclohexane	Nil
75 " + 25 "	-180	Carbon tetrachloride	-5
50 " + 50 "	-95	Acetophenone (pure)	Nil

DISCUSSION

The rise and decay of photopotentials are shown in Fig. 2. It will be seen from the

FIG. 2. Photopotential-time curves for 0.012*M* acetophenone in alcohols with platinum as an indicator electrode.

Curves 1—3 refer respectively to EtOH, PrOH, and Bu.OH.

Curve 4 refers to EtOH with Ag as indicator electrode.

curve that this rise is comparatively slow with respect to the decay. The photopotential reaches a maximum value and this is maintained as long as the radiation is incident. Table I records the maximum photopotentials observed with various solvents. No photopotentials were observed with solvent alone.

Table I shows that the photopotentials are observed in polar solvents and only in those solvents which contain alcoholic group. Incidentally, Beckett and Porter⁹ in investigating the photochemical reaction of benzophe-

none in various solvents found the quantum yield of disappearance of benzophenone dependent on the solvent. Thus with isopropanol, the value was 1.98 molar einstein⁻¹; whereas addition of benzene decreased this value. This has been explained on the basis of ease of hydrogen abstraction from the solvent. The phenomenon possibly is the same in acetophenone systems also.

Table II records the effect of electrode material on the maximum photopotentials observed.

TABLE II
0.012M Acetophenone in EtOH.

Electrode	..	Pt	Gold plated Pt	Ni	Ag	Cu
Max. photopotential (mv)	..	-210	-160	-30	-11.5	Nil

The photopotentials are dependent on the electrode material and the highest values obtained are with noble metals. The low values, obtained with base metal electrodes, are probably due to presence of an oxide layer on the surface. Rosenthal *et al.*¹⁰, from the study of the effect of electrode material on the potential of quinhydrone electrode, have shown that base metals are erratic and provide low electrode potential values as the alternative reaction, namely, the reduction of oxide layer or the oxidation of metal, takes place at the interface. The photopotential is therefore expected to be maximum only when an inert electrode is used.

The photochemical reaction between acetophenone and isopropanol was investigated by Becket *et al.*¹¹, using the technique of flash photolysis. The formation of ketyl radical and its anion has been confirmed from spectroscopic data. Photochemical reaction in acetophenone/alcohol solution have been shown to be:

9. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 2038.

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **159**, 1795.

11. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 873.

Reaction (2) involves abstraction of hydrogen atom by excited acetophenone molecule from alcohol molecule. This reaction hardly takes place in solvents like benzene and cyclohexane. Using an irradiated d.m.e. in alkaline benzophenone-isopropanol medium, Berg and Schwirs^{1,2} observed a reversible reduction-oxidation wave for the conversion of ketyl radical anion to benzophenone. Surash and Hercules⁶, using 9:10 anthraquinone in ethanol medium have observed photopotentials which have been attributed to the radical/anthraquinone equilibrium. That the photopotentials are produced because of electro-active species formed in solution during irradiation has been confirmed by us in the following way. This was done by using a bent-tube platinum electrode and keeping it away from the light beam. The light was then switched off and the electrode slowly rotated. The meter registered the photopotentials when the electrode came into the previously irradiated space and the decay curve was found to be identical with that recorded earlier. The photopotentials were observed to fall when the solution in the vicinity of the electrode was stirred. The effect of viscosity by adding pure glycerine to the solution on photopotentials is shown in Fig. 3.

FIG. 3 Effect of viscosity on photopotential-time curve of acetophenone in ethanol.

Curve 1 : 10% glycerol + 90% ethanol.

Curve 2 : 20% glycerol + 80% ethanol.

It is clear that the magnitude of the photopotential decreases with the viscosity though the nature of the rise and decay is essentially the same. Higher viscosity will mean less diffusion, resulting in better chances for collision for the radicals formed. Hence the net concentration of the radicals decreases with viscosity. The following electron-transfer reaction can be operative in solution under irradiation. The radical anion formed according to (3) above can get converted to the original acetophenone by the following mechanism:

or alternatively, radical anion can dimerise (as with benzophenone). Thus:

resulting in an equilibrium:

showing a two-electron transfer reaction mechanism.

Mechanism (I) read with equation (3) is similar to that advanced for the potential of quinhydrone electrode, assuming the intermediate formation of semiquinone ion for which spectroscopic evidence has been put forward by Bridge and Porter¹³. If this mechanism for photopotentials is accepted, the photopotentials should be pH-dependent. The influence of pH on the photopotential has been investigated and found that in alkaline solution the photopotentials even after long deoxygenation are positive. The presence of water in these solutions may lead to the formation of H₂O₂ during irradiation, resulting in positive photopotentials. It is therefore not possible at present to conclude as to the exact electron-transfer mechanism responsible for photopotentials.